

Temperature-dependent operation and wavelength tuning of a cryogenic Tm:CLNGG laser

Dominika Popelová¹, Karel Veselský¹, Jan Kratochvíl¹, Jan Šulc¹,
Helena Jelínková¹, María Dolores Serrano², Xiumei Han² and Carlos Zaldo²

1. Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Břehová 7, 115 19 Prague, Czech Republic

2. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid, CSIC, c/ Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz 3, 28049 Madrid, Spain

Authors' e-mail addresses: dominika.popelova@fffi.cvut.cz, dolores.serrano@icmm.csic.es

Abstract: Tm:CLNGG laser operation and wavelength tunability were demonstrated over a broad temperature range, from 80 K to 300 K. In the CW regime, an output power of 5 W was achieved and wide tunability was preserved at low temperatures.

Tm-doped tunable lasers operating in the eye-safe spectral region around 2 μm are important for a wide range of applications, including spectroscopy or atmospheric monitoring, where wavelength tuning enables accurate matching to absorption of gases, such as CO_2 or H_2O , as well as medical applications and further frequency conversion toward the mid-infrared [1,2]. Laser gain media with broad absorption and emission bands are attractive also for efficient diode pumping and for the generation of ultrashort laser pulses. Such broadband operation has been demonstrated in several classes of laser hosts, including fluorite-type CaF_2 crystals [3] and Lu_2O_3 transparent ceramics [4], or in compositional-disordered double tungstate ($\text{Na}^+/\text{Y}^{3+}$) [5], and GGAG garnet ($\text{Ga}^{3+}/\text{Al}^{3+}$) crystals [6]. One promising representative of the disordered crystal class is CLNGG, a Li-modified calcium niobium gallium garnet ($\text{Ca}_3\text{Li}_{0.275}\text{Nb}_{1.775}\text{Ga}_{2.95}\text{O}_{12}$), whose $\text{Nb}^{5+}/\text{Ga}^{3+}$ disordered structure leads to inhomogeneous broadening of the Tm^{3+} absorption and emission bands and thus supports broadly tunable laser operation around 2 μm . Gao et al. [7] demonstrated continuous-wave (CW) Tm:CLNGG laser operation with an output power of 1.6 W and a slope efficiency of 37%. Later, Pan et al. [8] reported 1.32 W in the CW regime with a slope efficiency of 46% and achieved wavelength tuning over 224 nm. Both experiments were performed at room temperature with water-cooling.

One key issue for tunable Tm-doped solid-state lasers operating around 2 μm is thermal management. Their quasi-three-level character can make room-temperature operation sensitive to reabsorption losses and thermally induced effects. Cryogenic cooling can mitigate these limitations by improving heat removal from the active medium and by reducing the thermo-optic and thermal expansion coefficients, which leads to weaker thermal lensing and lower thermally induced stress [9]. However, cooling reduces the absorption and emission bandwidths of the active media leading to pump instabilities and a reduced wavelength tunability. In disordered hosts, such as CLNGG, inhomogeneous broadening helps to preserve a sufficiently broad gain bandwidth even at reduced temperatures. This work investigates laser operation and wavelength tunability of Tm:CLNGG over the 80–300 K temperature range.

The investigated crystal was grown in air by the Czochralski technique using a platinum crucible. Details of the growth procedure have been given previously [10]. A Tm concentration of 5 at.% in the melt was used for the growth, resulting in a 6.05 at.% ($7.4 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) Tm concentration in the crystal. For the laser tests, a sample with a length of 6.7 mm and transverse dimensions of $3.94 \times 4.44 \text{ mm}^2$ was cut from the crystal boule, polished and left uncoated. The sample was wrapped in indium foil for better thermal contact and mounted in a Janis Research liquid nitrogen cryostat equipped with CaF_2 windows.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of the Tm:CLNGG laser. The MgF_2 birefringent filter was used only in the wavelength tuning configuration.

Figure 1 shows the experimental setup used for laser characterization. The Tm:CLNGG active medium was resonantly pumped by a BrightLase Ultra-100 laser diode from QPC Lasers operating at $\lambda_p = 1680 \text{ nm}$. The pump radiation was delivered through a fiber with $400 \mu\text{m}$ of core diameter and focused into the crystal using 1:1 focusing

optics. A hemispherical laser resonator was constructed, consisting of a flat pump mirror and a spherical output coupler with a radius of curvature of 150 mm. For the measurement of power characteristics, an output coupler with a reflectivity of 93.6% at 2 μm was used, whereas the wavelength tuning experiments were performed with a higher-reflectivity output coupler of 98.4%. Wavelength tuning was achieved using a 1-mm-thick MgF_2 birefringent filter inserted into the resonator at the Brewster angle.

The laser power characteristics are shown in Figure 2(a). At a crystal temperature of 80 K, the laser was characterized in CW operation, reaching a maximum output power of 5 W with a slope efficiency of 37.3%. The laser operated at a wavelength of 1996 nm. At higher crystal temperatures of 200 K and 300 K, stable CW operation was limited by thermally induced effects. Therefore, the laser performance was measured in a quasi-continuous-wave (QCW) regime using pulsed pumping with a repetition rate of 10 Hz and a pump pulse duration of 15 ms. The plotted QCW output power corresponds to the calculated power amplitude in the pulsed regime. The corresponding slope efficiencies decreased to 21.2% at 200 K and 7.8% at 300 K, indicating a significant increase in thermal effects with increasing temperature.

The wavelength tunability of the $\text{Tm}:\text{CLNGG}$ laser was investigated in a pulsed regime. Broad continuous tuning around 2 μm was achieved over the full temperature range of 80–300 K, with tuning intervals varying from 89 nm at 80 K to 127 nm at 250 K, as shown in Figure 2(b). At low temperatures, an additional tuning region appeared near 1.87 μm ; however, it vanished as the crystal temperature increased. The measured tuning ranges are also limited by the transmission of the output coupler, which increased toward both edges of the tuning ranges.

Figure 2: Laser performance of the resonantly diode-pumped $\text{Tm}:\text{CLNGG}$: (a) CW operation at 80 K, and QCW operation at 200 K and 300 K. (b) Wavelength tuning range at different temperatures. $\lambda_p=1680$ nm.

In conclusion, $\text{Tm}:\text{CLNGG}$ was demonstrated as a promising gain medium for tunable laser operation around 2 μm under cryogenic cooling. At 80 K, the laser delivered up to 5 W of output power in the CW regime, which is, to the best of our knowledge, the highest CW output power reported so far for a $\text{Tm}:\text{CLNGG}$ laser. The achieved wavelength tuning over the investigated temperature range shows that the disordered CLNGG host can retain a broad tuning range even at reduced temperatures.

References

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